

Advancement in Technology and Its Encounter With Tradition : Medical Techniques and Female Foeticide

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Abstract

Is our society handling the advancement in technology in right way? Never before have there been so many medical intervention options available to determine the well being of the foetus. Advancements in reproductive technology are encouraging and have given newfound hope to couples who may not have had these same opportunities just a few years ago. However, the society with deep-seated cultural preference for sons have misused this beautiful advancement in technology and hence skewed the sex ratio in various states of India. Advances in technologies, especially ultrasonography are now conveniently available at the “clinic next door”, with the woman’s family willing to dish out any amount that is demanded. The present article aims to reflect upon the advancement in technology and its impact on adverse child sex ratio. The article also tried to explore the possible options to counter this critical medico-social problem.

Keywords : Female Foeticide; pre-natal diagnostic tests

Introduction

Progress of science and technology is mandatory for the progress of a nation, but what matters most is its manifestation and beneficial application. Advancement in technology has played an important and constructive role in the area of reproductive biology. However on the other hand this advancement has put its adverse effect on child sex ratio. In India and China, which both need low cost alternatives for diagnosis and treatment, ultrasound use is regulated because of the common practice of using it to determine sex of the fetus and then to selectively abort female foetuses [1]. Social pressures in India, and the presence of low-cost technologies like ultrasound, have led to sex-based abortion of female fetuses, and an increasingly smaller percentage of girls born each year. In China, the one-child law combined with a preference for male children led to female feticide [2]

A ban on the government departments at the centre and in the states, making use of pre-natal sex determination for the purpose of abortion — a penal offence — led to the commercialization of the technology; private clinics providing sex determination tests through amniocentesis multiplied rapidly and widely. These tests are made available in areas that do not even have potable water, with marginal farmers willing to take loans at 25 per cent interest to have the test. Advertisements appear blatantly encouraging people to abort their female fetuses in order to save the future cost of dowry. The portable ultrasound machine has allowed doctors to go from house to house in towns and villages. In a democracy it is difficult to restrict right to business and livelihood if the usual parameters are fulfilled.

The present article aims to reflect upon the advancement in technology and its impact on adverse child sex ratio. The article also tried to explore the possible options to counter this critical medico-social problem.

Medical Advancement in the area of Pre-natal Diagnostic Tests and Its Misuse

The three chief pre-natal diagnostic tests that are being used to determine the sex of a fetus are amniocentesis, chronic villi biopsy (CVB) and ultrasonography . Amniocentesis is meant to be used in high-risk pregnancies, in women over 35 years. CVB is meant to diagnose inherited diseases like thalassaemia, cystic fibrosis and muscular dystrophy. Ultrasonography is the most commonly used technique. It is non-invasive and can identify up to 50 per cent of abnormalities related to the central nervous system of the fetus. But sexing has become its preferred application

Chorionic villus sampling (CVS) and amniocentesis may be conducted in the eighth and ninth week, onwards. During chorionic villus sampling, a sample of the chorionic villus (which is a tissue of the placenta, the organ that connects the foetus to the uterine wall, to supply it with nutrients and gas, and to enable waste excretion) is obtained, and tested. This

is generally used to test the foetus for chromosomal or genetic disorders. In amniocentesis, a little of the amniotic fluid (present in the amniotic sac, surrounding the foetus) is extracted. This fluid contains foetal tissues, and the DNA present in them is tested for chromosomal abnormalities, and foetal infection. Both these techniques can be used to determine the sex of the foetus. However, these techniques are rather invasive, and lead to severe chances of damage to the foetus and miscarriage [3]. These techniques are also relatively difficult.

The amniocentesis test has achieved dubious popularity as the one which provides quick ‘results’ and is ‘accurate’. Health-wise, these tests can cause a great deal of damage. Very often, the clinical preconditions of following aseptic procedures and ultrasonic monitoring are not followed during the incision and piercing of the amniotic sac for amniotic fluid. This leads to high chances of sepsis in the reproductive tract, hip dislocation and respiratory problems [4]. This test can also cause considerable damage to the foetus and placenta, resulting in spontaneous abortion or premature labour [5]. However, the commercial viability of these tests and the glamour of being in the medical business have overtaken ethical considerations. Medical practitioners conceal the fact that these tests ‘detect’ but do not ‘determine’ the sex of the foetus. Therefore, having an abortion or multiple abortions in the sixteenth and eighteenth week (third month and after) of pregnancy if the foetus is of the ‘wrong’ sex is risky; and the test is not always foolproof. Further, this puts the woman’s health at stake. The news of the death of a woman 20 weeks pregnant after an abortion following an amniocentesis in a private clinic in Bombay, illustrates the unacknowledged risk that is involved [6]. Moreover, selective abortions following the SD test after the twelfth week of pregnancy is gross misuse of a liberal legislation. The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971, permits abortion up to the twelfth week of pregnancy. However, amniocentesis can be performed only during the fourteenth and sixteenth week of pregnancy and an abortion thereafter can be conducted only between the fifteenth and eighteenth week of pregnancy.

The use of ultrasound has had a large impact on health care in resource poor countries [7]. Using an ultrasound to determine how dehydrated a child is, whether an injured person requires surgery, whether a person who has collapsed has a blood clot or a punctured lung or fluid around their heart and treat those things appropriately is incredibly powerful and, after paying for the machine, costs nothing but the time to train practitioners. The misuse of ultrasound in India for sex determination, leading to female foeticide, has prompted a debate in the radiological community about who should be allowed to perform ultrasound exams. And whether restricting it to only radiologists and gynaecologists will help curb its illegal and wrongful use. The widespread misuse of prenatal ultrasound has led to genocide against the female gender. In India, due to fetal sexing, a female fetus is selectively aborted every 12 seconds. As long as multinational corporations continue to sell cheap ultrasound machines to developing countries, and while the law permits abortion and society maintains a preference for sons over daughters, the illegal practice of fetal sex determination will continue.

Above all, indisputably, ultrasound technology is an invaluable tool for medical diagnosis and cannot be banned. However, a more nuanced solution exists: creating safer ultrasound machines that cannot be misused.

Where is the cure?

Manufacturers of ultrasound machines have patented software that can automatically prevent the sex of a fetus from being revealed, while retaining all other medical information [8]. A patent search demonstrates that technology to specifically block the genital organ in a live ultrasound is known to various multinational companies. The existence of these patents clearly demonstrates the ability of ultrasound manufacturers to create ultrasound machines that block the genitalia — thus producing a far safer ultrasound. This “add-on” patented software for preventing sex-determination would be effective and relatively inexpensive. Yet it has not been widely introduced or implemented. General Electric (GE) has a pending US patent application (US Patent Publication 20090169074) entitled, “System and Method for Computer Assisted Analysis of Medical Image,” which concerns technology that allows selected information, such as the genitals, to be suppressed. GE’s patent application states: “When required by law, a display of real-time ultrasound exam of a fetus can be designed to suppress sex determination task, by selectively blurring images of genitals of the fetus.” There is a counterpart application by GE, pending in China. Philips’ patent application, CN102048557, entitled, “Device Capable of Preventing the Abuse of Ultrasonic Image Inspection and Method Thereof,” is also pending in China. Shenzhen Microprofit Electronics owns Chinese Patent CN100462054 entitled, “Method for Shielding Sex Part on Foetus Image for Preventing and Recognizing

Foetus Sex.”

Interestingly, none of these patents have been filed in India. Is it because the filing would be an admission to the Indian government that these companies do have technology to prevent sex-determination? Also, if these patents are just a click away, why is the Indian government not taking a stand?

Even though the Indian government has outlawed both sex-determination and sex-selective abortion since 1994, and has mandated that ultrasound manufacturers sell the machines only to licensed clinics, the number of female fetuses aborted has grown exponentially each year. In the last 30 years, since the use of ultrasounds in India began, the child sex ratio has fallen from 962 girls per 1,000 boys in 1981, to merely 919 girls to 1,000 boys in 2011 – a massive 48 point drop. Moreover, skewed sex ratios drive women to even lower social status, increasing violence against women.

There would undoubtedly be challenges to implementing and distributing new ultrasound machines that automatically block information on fetal genitalia (8). In very rare cases, there is the likelihood of blocking a pathological lesion present near the genital organs. This, however, can be addressed with simple innovations, such as sending unblocked fetal genital images to a certified image review center through a secured network.

Many questions still remain, however: What should be done with the thousands of ultrasound machines that are already in use in India? Can the government demand that owners update the existing machines with the software? Who will do the updating?

Ultimately, collaboration between manufacturers, third-party software developers, and the government is required to successfully attain the unified goal of curbing female feticide.

That being said, a technological solution alone cannot provide a cure for deeper social issues such as an inherent preference for a son. But as ultrasound accounts for 95 percent of prenatal sex-determination, a technological block would directly disable the overt crime of sex determination.

Currently, thousands of mothers in India are coerced by their husbands and in-laws to abort their female child. To empower mothers and attack the problem head-on, we must provide the technology for preventing sex-selective abortion, and this may further catalyze social transformation.

Societal responsibility falls just as much on corporations as it does on citizens and governments. In response to strong criticisms by the United Nations and other international organizations, GE released a report in 2009 stating that it would “move beyond vigilance of its own operations and think creatively about how the Company can contribute to the wider societal change that must take place.” Yet the most promising solution is not actively pursued. It is time for corporations to show leadership and lead the call to action.

Together, multinational companies such as GE, Siemens, and Philips, hold 72 percent of a rapidly growing ultrasound market in India. The costs for bringing the genital-blocking technology to the market certainly do not outweigh the benefits. These companies have the ethical responsibility of solving an international social crisis.

Before sex ratios plummet further and rapes occur at tragically increasing rates, the life-saving ultrasound technology must be upgraded to prevent its misuse.

Conclusion

Innovation and inventions are a natural part of today’s developing world – and these cannot be blamed for the consequences our uses lead to. However, it is our usage and the exploitation of the resources we have (like we do in nearly every field), that hurts us the most. It is this usage that has to be checked and kept under control, if we have to find a solution to the problems we are facing. However, to do so, it is of utmost importance, to firstly, investigate and figure out why this is happening, and what has led and motivated us to take such undue advantages of the results of our very own ‘brainpower’.

References

1. Ahmad, N. *Female feticide in India. Issues Law Med.* 2010; 26(1):13-29.

2. George, S.M. "Millions of missing girls: from fetal sexing to high technology sex selection in India". *Prenat Diagn.* 2006 ; 26(7):604-9.
3. Grinshpun-Cohen, J. Miron-Shatz, T. Berkenstet, M. Pras, E. The limited effect of information on Israeli pregnant women at advanced maternal age who decide to undergo amniocentesis. *Isr J Health Policy Res.* 2015; 17: 4:23.
4. Ravindra, R.P. 'The Scarcer Half: A Report on Amniocentesis and Other Sex-Determination Techniques, Sex Preselection and New Re-productive Technologies', Counterfact No. 9. 1986, CED Health Feature, January.
5. Dube, Leela. 'Misadventures in Amniocentesis', *Economic and Political Weekly*, 1983; 19, February: 279-80.
6. Natarajan, S. 'Ban Female Foeticide', *Femina*, 1986-87; December 23- January 7.
7. Ghosh, R. Sharma, A.K. Missing female fetus: a micro level investigation of sex determination in a periurban area of Northern India.. *Health Care Women Int.* 2012; 33(11):1020-34.
8. Davey, N. Devalaraja, S. Davey, S. A New Way to Curb Female Feticide. *Fair Observer: Make Sense of the world.* 2013; Sep 9.